

D5.5 Report on engagement of researchers 1

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Acronym Glossary

Acronym	Full Form
AASE	African Association of Science Editors
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AJOL	African Journals Online
ALMASI	Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit OA Publishing Services Internationally
APCs	Article Processing Charges
ASAPbio	Accelerating Science And Publication In Biology
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CoP	Community of Practice
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERUA	European Reform University Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FECYT	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y Tecnología
FORRT	Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training
GYA	Global Young Academy
HQ	Headquarter

IGSG-CNR	Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems of National Research Council (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)
INBIRS	Instituto de Investigaciones Biomédicas en Retrovirus y SIDA
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement
MCAA	Marie Curie Alumni Association
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NASA TOPS	National Aeronautics and Space Administration Transform to Open Science
NCCs	National Capacity Centers
OA	Open Access
OJS	Open Journals Systems
OLS	Open Life Science
PCI	Peer Community In
PLOS	Public Library of Science
RUN-EU PLUS	Regional University Network European University -Professional Research Programmes for Business and Society
SciELO	Scientific Electronic Library Online
SPARC EUROPE	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition EUROPE
UN	United Nations
YERUN	Young European Research Universities Network

Executive summary

Deliverable D5.5 reports on the first phase of researcher engagement carried out under Task 5.3 of the ALMASI project, covering the period from January 2025 to June 2026. The task was designed as a two-phase effort: the first eighteen months were dedicated to establishing the infrastructure and relationships needed for sustained engagement, while the remaining period will be dedicated to active delivery. This report discusses the outputs of the first phase.

Engagement framework established

By the end of 2025, the following framework was put in place to serve the delivery phase:

- Workstream 1: The ALMASI Ambassador Programme was designed and launched through an open call running from 17 November 2025 to 15 January 2026.
- Workstream 2: The Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing was introduced with its first event, *Reclaiming Knowledge: Why Diamond Open Access Matters*, delivered on 11 December 2025 in co-operation with the Global Young Academy.
- A cross-work-package stakeholder mapping exercise was developed, to support both pathways by tracking opportunities for partnerships with researcher communities, infrastructure providers, and policy actors.

Reach and cohort composition

The response to both workstreams (the Ambassador programme and the Discussion Series) exceeded initial expectations and required substantive adaptations to the programme's design:

- The ALMASI Ambassador Programme attracted 155 applications from more than thirty countries and confirmed 114 ambassadors. Of these, 61 became active participants over the course of seven launch sessions held in March 2026.
- The Ambassador cohort was geographically weighted toward Africa, although there was representation in each of the three core ALMASI regions. Conversion rates from application to active participation were higher in Europe and Latin America than in Africa, partially offsetting the imbalance observed at the application stage.
- Design adaptations included shifting from competitive selection to an expression-of-interest framework, moving from one-to-one to group-based mentoring, and the introduction of a screening step in the application process.
- The first webinar reached 255 registrations with a geographic mix spanning Europe, Africa, Latin America, and a smaller cohort from North America and Asia, and a

professional audience dominated by library and information services staff, researchers and academics, and publishing and editorial professionals.

- The second webinar, held on 11 June 2026 on the Publish-Review-Curate model, drew 414 registrations, with Europe and Latin America each accounting for just over a third of registrations and a substantial African contingent.

Added value for researchers and publishers

Drawing on the talking points articulated during the first webinar and aligned with the work of Deliverable D5.2, the report synthesises the added value of Diamond Open Access around the following themes:

- For researchers: access without financial barriers; rights retention and author control; equity and participation in global science; and alignment with the public mission of research.
- For publishers and advocates: defining Diamond Open Access through governance and ownership rather than fees alone; advocating for research assessment reform as inseparable from Diamond Open Access; pursuing rights retention at the institutional and national level; investing in shared infrastructure, training, and quality; and communicating clearly about sustainability to secure coordinated funding.

Moving forward

Over the next phase of the project (M18–M36), the focus will be on delivery across both workstreams:

- Ambassadors will engage in local and regional events, mentoring sessions, translation and co-authorship, glossary work, and advocacy through peer communication.
- The Discussion Series will continue beyond the second webinar, with future themes shaped by the literature on researcher engagement and by priorities surfacing within researcher communities, including peer review platforms and the role of artificial intelligence in scholarly communication.
- In collaboration with Task 3.1, ambassadors will contribute to sprints by developing and reviewing training materials, extending their role from outreach to active co-creation of ALMASI's educational outputs.
- The final report, D5.10, due in month thirty-six, will assess the outcomes of this delivery phase against the engagement targets to which Task 5.3 contributes.

1. Introduction

The ALMASI project (*Aligning and Mutualising Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally*) brings together 16 partners¹ from Africa, Europe, and Latin America to strengthen the Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem. Running from January 2025 to December 2027, the project addresses a fundamental challenge in scholarly communication: ensuring that the infrastructure for research dissemination serves the global research community equitably, free of financial barriers for both authors and readers.

Within this broader effort, Task 5.3, *Engagement Strategy for Researchers via Editor Communities*, is responsible for encouraging researchers to publish in nonprofit and Diamond OA journals. The task operates through two complementary workstreams: the **Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing**, a public-facing webinar series that explores key themes in community-driven publishing, and the **ALMASI Ambassador Programme**, a peer-driven network of researchers, editors, librarians, and research support professionals who advocate for Diamond OA within their own communities and institutions. We will explore both of these in detail.

This deliverable, D5.5, reports on the engagement work carried out through Task 5.3 and associated efforts within the wider project, during the first 18 months of the project. It responds to two core questions set out in the ALMASI Description of Action:

- What are the key added values for researchers who publish in nonprofit and Diamond OA journals?
- How can publishers better communicate these added values to the research community?

To engage meaningfully with researchers, it was decided to create a structured approach to reach out to communities. This report focuses primarily on the preparatory efforts and rationale that led the project to produce the two workstreams towards engagement. Consequently, the wider impact and outreach efforts will be better represented in the second version of this report, due in December 2027.

More accurately, the period covered by this report (January 2025 to June 2026) describes background and context on researchers' engagement, strategic planning and initial programme delivery. The report is structured as follows. **Section 2** sets out the background and rationale for a dedicated researcher engagement strategy, connecting the work with previous efforts within ALMASI and specifically the Deliverable D5.3 and the general approach towards stakeholders. **Section 3** describes the methodology and approach, including stakeholder mapping, design principles, and the strategic decisions that shaped

¹ See the full list of consortium partners in the ALMASI Website:
<https://almasiproject.org/the-consortium/>

both workstreams. **Section 4** provides a detailed account of the engagement activities undertaken: the Discussion Series and the Ambassador Programme. **Section 5** synthesises the key added values for researchers and publishers that emerged from the engagement work, mainly drawing on webinar discussions and advocacy materials developed within the project. It gathers the insights into talking points that can be leveraged by either researchers or publishers to promote and advocate for Diamond OA. **Section 6** looks ahead to the remaining activities and outlines how the engagement network will continue to develop through to the end of the project.

Throughout, the report reflects a principle that has guided the task from the outset: that effective engagement with researchers is best achieved not through top-down messaging but through collaborative, peer-driven approaches that respect the diversity of research cultures, languages, and institutional contexts across the ALMASI partnership.

A note on contribution to project KPIs

The activities reported in this deliverable contribute directly to two of ALMASI's engagement targets:

- **Researcher engagement target.** The project commits to ensuring that at least ten per cent of people engaged through Task 5.3 activities (webinars, the Ambassador Programme, and community events) are researchers, across Africa, Europe, and Latin America. Task 5.3 is one of the principal instruments through which that target is pursued, with the Ambassador Programme and the Discussion Series, together, designed to reach researchers and editors across all three regions.
- **Event participation target.** The project (overall) commits to twenty online events over its duration, with an average of twenty participants per workshop and a minimum of one hundred participants for larger, organised events. The first webinar in the Discussion Series and the launch sessions of the Ambassador Programme contribute to this target, as reported in the Engagement Activities section that follows.

D5.5 is itself part of the project's monitoring architecture for these targets.

2. Background and Rationale

Institutional engagement and its grassroots complement

ALMASI's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy (D5.3) (Debano et al., 2025) identifies seven primary stakeholder groups whose engagement is essential to

building a globally aligned nonprofit OA publishing ecosystem: (1) Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Academies of Science; (2) scholarly societies; (3) libraries; (4) Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs); (5) Research Funding Organisations (RFOs); (6) regional, national, and international Open Science policymakers; and (7) the wider OA support community. Taken together, these groups constitute the formal institutional spaces within which Diamond OA can be embedded, sustained, and scaled. They are where publishing services are located, where research is assessed, where funding flows are decided, and where Open Science policy is set.

ALMASI's engagement architecture is built around these institutional partners. WP1 maps publishing services and solutions across the three regions; WP2 develops aligned quality support instruments for IPSPs; WP3 produces training pathways and curricula for editors and journal staff; and WP4 convenes the policy and funder fora that engage institutional leaders, ministries, and policymakers. This is, by design, a largely top-down approach, intended to shift the structural conditions under which nonprofit publishing operates.

Task 5.3, and the engagement work this report documents, occupies a different position within that approach. Its target audiences overlap substantially with the stakeholder groups defined in D5.3, but T5.3 applies a grassroots strategy (bottom-up). Its two principal mechanisms, the Ambassador Programme and the Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing, engage the people who populate those institutions: researchers from all disciplines and career stages, librarians, research support staff, journal editors, and editorial board members. Ambassadors are themselves embedded in the institutional spaces identified by D5.3, and the Discussion Series is conceived as a convergence space where these communities meet across the three regions, rather than as a channel through which policy is communicated to them.

These grassroots initiatives matter because institutional change in scholarly publishing rarely happens by policy alone. Even where Diamond OA receives formal endorsement at the funder or ministerial level, take-up depends on the choices of individual researchers about where to submit their work, of individual editors about how to run their journals, and of individual librarians and research support staff about which routes to recommend. Engaging these constituencies as agents within the system, rather than as recipients of decisions made elsewhere, is what T5.3 is designed to do. D5.5 reports on how that engagement has been built during the first eighteen months of the project, and on what it has revealed about the conditions for community uptake of nonprofit publishing across Africa, Europe, and Latin America.

3. Methodology and Approach

The methodology section highlights key aspects of the preparation of the two approaches towards engagement. As outlined in the introduction, the task is split into two. The first

eighteen months were dedicated to designing the infrastructure and relationships needed for sustained researcher engagement, while the subsequent period will provide more concrete outcomes. To build the basis for research engagement going forward, two interconnected workstreams were developed: **an Ambassador Programme** to act as a multiplier for reaching researcher and editor communities at scale, and **a Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing** designed as a public space where communities meet one another to share knowledge, insights, challenges and successes of Diamond OA activities, from the perspective of researchers. In parallel, we have developed a **stakeholder database** to better help us plan, track and monitor engagement with policy makers, infrastructure providers, publishers, and researcher communities.

The Ambassador Programme

An ALMASI ambassador network extends the project's presence into regional and disciplinary communities. It creates a reciprocal channel through which ALMASI can listen to the realities of publishing in different researcher contexts.

The mobilisation of researchers and editors as ambassadors has become an established feature of European research and open science initiatives over the past decade, offering a body of practical experience on which ALMASI could draw. Among university alliances and networks, the ERUA (European Reform University Alliance) Open Science Ambassador Programme (Kralj et al., 2025) and the RUN-EU PLUS (Regional University Network | European University - **P**rofessional Research Programmes for **B**usiness and **S**ociety) Network of Open Science Ambassadors (Vorarlberg University of Applied Sciences, 2022) have each recruited researcher-ambassadors across partner institutions to advance open science locally, while the YERUN Full Open Science Ambassadors² initiative adopted a recognition-based model in which research teams earn ambassador status by meeting OA publishing thresholds. At the project level, the FAIR-IMPACT project selected thirteen EOSC FAIR Champions³ through an open call to act as multipliers and disseminators of project results. The ALMASI model drew on these programmes together with the experience of the DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) Ambassadors network⁴, focusing squarely on the editorial and researcher communities at the centre of the Diamond OA ecosystem.

Initially, we were discussing a smaller cohort of ambassadors, in line with established practices described earlier. The team ultimately decided to reframe the call as an expression of interest rather than a competitive selection.

² YERUN. (2024, October 16). *Open Science ambassadors*. Young European Research Universities Network. <https://yerun.eu/2024/10/open-science-ambassadors/>

³ FAIR-IMPACT. (n. d.). *EOSC FAIR Champions*. Retrieved April 24, 2026, from <https://fair-impact.eu/eosc-fair-champions>

⁴ DOAJ. (n.d.). *Ambassadors*. Directory of Open Access Journals. Retrieved April 24, 2026, from <https://doaj.org/about/ambassadors/>

On the nature of engagement, we agreed that the programme should be voluntary and digital, that ALMASI would not be able to provide travel funding for ambassadorial activities, and that activities should focus on Diamond OA advocacy, co-organisation of local events, translation of key outputs, blog contribution, and mentoring. To prepare for the launch, we created an application form, an announcement text, and a simplified selection process that reflected the expression-of-interest framing. The results of this process are discussed in Section 4.

The Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing

The rationale for the Discussion Series was distinct from the policy and funding focus of other parts of the project. The series was designed as a public space in which researchers, editors, and publishers engage with one another on questions that shape the Diamond OA ecosystem. The emphasis throughout was on amplifying researcher voices and creating conditions for sustained dialogue across regions with a specific emphasis on nonprofit publishing.

Discussion around the series was developed in several iterations. Initially, we envisaged a broader programme of thematic workshops covering reviewer pools, funding and policy, publishing models and peer review, technological platforms, and metadata and indexing. At times, this was inspired by the know-how and experience of the project's partners. Early on it was recognised that the series must work with and be more inspired by what researchers need to discuss rather than the other way around. The team concluded that a simpler approach would be more realistic and effective, and decided to plan one webinar at a time, reassessing priority areas after each event rather than committing to a fixed series of themes in advance.

Linguistic and regional diversity were also discussed. The group considered whether to run separate regional webinars or to favour cross-regional events with multilingual representation among speakers, preferring the latter with the understanding that subsequent sessions could be organised in other languages as language teams emerged. On the relationship between the webinars and the Ambassador Programme, the conclusion was that smaller, more localised events organised through the ambassador network would complement the public webinars rather than compete with them.

Integration of the two workstreams

Taken together, the Ambassador Programme and the Discussion Series form the backbone of the T5.3 engagement methodology. Ambassadors will provide access across regions and disciplinary contexts, while the series provides a structure for discussing Diamond OA matters from a researcher's perspective in an evolving manner. Ambassadors should help disseminate and localise webinar content, and themes raised in webinar discussions inform the topics explored in ambassador mentoring sessions and local events. This mutual

reinforcement is the core design feature that the subsequent chapters document in terms of actual activities, reach, and lessons learned.

Stakeholder Identification and Mapping

It was mentioned before in the report that a core target group are researchers. The primary objective is to continue reaching out to researchers and their communities to engage with Diamond OA, e.g. to encourage them to publish in such venues. As part of ALMASI's wider efforts, a stakeholder database has been created. The rationale for the stakeholder database is described in more detail in D5.8 (Debano et al., 2026). Partners conducted an extensive landscape mapping to identify all possible directions for collaboration as part of the project.

The following table describes a few key stakeholders to support with researcher engagement:

Stakeholder	Type & Reach	Relevance to ALMASI
Global Young Academy (GYA)	Professional network, global / cross-regional (Headquarter (HQ) Germany); around 200 early and mid-career researchers from 85+ countries	Strong voice for Global South ECRs (Early Career Researcher) in science policy and open access. Active Open Science working group running the First Fridays lecture series and research on barriers for ECRs. Holds a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with PLOS (Public Library of Science), sits within the InterAcademy Partnership, and provides advice to the United Nations (UN). Existing collaboration with ALMASI.
MetaDocencia	Researcher-led community, Latin America (Argentina); Spanish-speaking open science training community	Delivers NASA TOPS ⁵ Open Science 101 cohorts in Spanish for Latin America, strongly aligning with ALMASI learning pathways (T3.1). It is directly relevant to the Latin American ambassador cohort.
ASAPbio (Accelerating Science And Publication In Biology)	Researcher-led community, global / cross-regional (United States); scientist-led nonprofit	Promotes preprints and open peer review in the life sciences and runs a Fellows Programme with a global community. Offers potential synergy with the Discussion Series and ambassador peer exchange.

⁵ NASA TOPS: NASA's Transform to Open Science initiative, whose Open Science 101 curriculum supports open-science training.

Peer Community In (PCI)	Infrastructure provider, Europe (France); nonprofit founded by INRAE (Institut national de recherche pour l'agriculture, l'alimentation et l'environnement) researchers in 2017	Operates more than 20 thematic communities that provide free peer review and recommendations for preprints, alongside the Peer Community Journal (Diamond OA). Open source infrastructure that is free for authors and readers, and a core example of the Diamond OA model ALMASI promotes. Directly relevant to the Discussion Series on peer review and Diamond OA alternatives, and to learning pathways for editor training. French institutional roots provide a Francophone connection.
Open Life Science (OLS)	Researcher-led community, global / cross-regional (United Kingdom); nonprofit	Runs Open Seeds, a 16-week cohort-based mentoring and training programme creating Open Science ambassadors, with more than 8 cohorts completed and over 300 mentees trained globally, including strong Global South participation. Partnered with NASA TOPS alongside MetaDocencia. Its ambassador model closely mirrors the ALMASI programme structure, making it directly relevant to learning pathways, ambassador training methodology, and community building. It also serves as a fiscal sponsor for other open science projects.
PREreview	Infrastructure provider, global / cross-regional (United States); nonprofit platform	Community-driven open preprint peer review platform running Open Reviewers workshops, Live Reviews, a Champions Programme, and PREreview Clubs globally. Supports more than 29 preprint servers and covers reviews in English, Spanish, and Portuguese. Founded by women scientists with a focus on equity for early-career and historically excluded researchers; funded by the Gates Foundation, CZI, and Wellcome. Directly relevant to the Discussion Series (open peer review), learning pathways (reviewer training), and ambassador engagement through the PREreview Clubs model.
FORRT (Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training)	Infrastructure provider, global / cross-regional (Germany); community-driven pedagogical initiative	Community-driven pedagogical infrastructure for open and reproducible science, offering open educational resources, syllabi, and a curated resource nexus. Strong alignment with ALMASI learning pathways (T3.1) and curriculum development, with social justice and Global South inclusion as explicit priorities.
African Association of Science Editors (AASE)	Professional network, Africa (continental)	Professional community for science editors across Africa, promoting editorial standards, training, and publishing quality on the continent. Holds a formal link with EASE. Directly represents the editor community that ALMASI ambassadors will engage with, and is a core audience for the T5.3 engagement strategy and learning pathways editor training.

Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)	Professional network, global / cross-regional (HQ Belgium); alumni community of Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions fellows with members across 150+ countries	Large cross-disciplinary network of researchers at all career stages with strong European institutional roots and global alumni reach. Active working groups, including on Open Science and Research Impact, offer channels for engaging both ECRs and established researchers around Diamond OA, open peer review, and policy advocacy. Potential synergy with the Discussion Series and ambassador programme through its multiplier capacity across European and international research communities.
European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc)	International federation of 28 national organisations of PhD candidates, and more generally of junior researchers from 25 countries of the European Union and the Council of Europe	Active at the European and national levels, it advances OA and open science through its work. Has two relevant Working Groups on AI (Artificial Intelligence), Open Science and Research Assessment and Equitable Opportunities and Sustainable Research Cultures.
Diamond OA publishing in the African Community of Practice	A professional network that includes 387 Diamond OA journal editors and publishers	Provides a platform to communicate with author and reviewer communities.

Table 1. Key stakeholders to support with researcher engagement

The rationale is to reach out to many of these communities with the view to create formal partnerships and collaboration proposals, and to seek opportunities for researchers to participate in our activities as speakers in webinars, for example, or in other ways.

Limitations and Adaptations

Several constraints surfaced during the design phase and shaped the approach that was ultimately adopted.

Internal capacity for mentoring. The original concept anticipated a cohort in which individual mentoring and support were feasible. The move to a larger, more geographically diverse group required a shift toward group mentoring, thematic sessions, and regional sprints rather than one-to-one arrangements.

Linguistic access. A substantial portion of the ambassador cohort indicated French as a preferred language, with further demand for Spanish and Portuguese. However, project resources to deliver sessions in these languages are limited and depend on the availability of

partners to lead them. We began the launch in English and decided to build language-specific strands progressively as partner capacity becomes available.

Thematic scope of the Discussion Series. Early plans envisaged a broad programme of workshops covering reviewer pools, funding, publishing models, technology, and indexing, but the combined load of other project events made this unrealistic. The team adapted by focusing on one carefully designed webinar at a time, treating each as an opportunity to test themes and formats before committing to further sessions.

4. Engagement Activities - Interim results

While this report primarily focuses on the preparatory nature of the activities, there are already results from the various engagement activities that can be reported on and discussed, and the potential impact of future activities. We will first discuss the first and second webinars on the Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing, and then the ambassador programme.

Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing

First Webinar

The first event in the Discussion Series, *Reclaiming Knowledge: Why Diamond Open Access Matters*, took place on 11 December 2025, aligning thematically with the International Open Access Week. This was co-hosted with the Global Young Academy.⁶

Theme, speakers, and outputs

The webinar featured three speakers from Africa, Europe, and Latin America to examine how Diamond Open Access can contribute to a more equitable, community-driven publishing ecosystem. The theme deliberately combined legal, structural, and lived-experience perspectives on the limitations of commercial publishing and the possibilities offered by community-owned, nonprofit alternatives, with particular attention to rights retention, research assessment, and the participation of researchers in low- and middle-income settings.

Dr Philip Mwachaka, Editor-in-Chief of the East African Journal of Neurological Sciences, opened from the African perspective with a talk titled *Opening the Gates: Building a Fairer Global Publishing System Through Diamond Access*, exploring how Diamond OA can dismantle structural publishing inequities and empower researchers in Africa and other low-resource settings to reclaim ownership of their scholarship.

⁶ The recording is available on the ALMASI YouTube channel at [Reclaiming knowledge: why Diamond Open Access matters](#), and the slides from all three presentations have [been deposited on Zenodo](#) ensuring that the material remains accessible beyond the live event.

Ginevra Peruginelli, Senior Researcher at the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems of National Research Council (IGSG-CNR) in Florence, contributed the European perspective on *Scientific knowledge and the public good: Rights, responsibilities and community-driven governance*, drawing on her work across European projects such as DIAMAS (Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication), and Right2Pub, to address rights retention, community governance, and the legal principles that underpin public-good publishing.

Dr Luciana Balboa, Infectious Diseases researcher at INBIRS (Instituto de Investigaciones Biomédicas en Retrovirus y SIDA, University of Buenos Aires-CONICET) and member of the Global Young Academy and the CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) board, brought the Latin American perspective in *Diversifying candidate profiles to tackle complex societal problems: The role of non-commercial publishing*, speaking from her first-hand experience of how a system dominated by Gold Open Access creates perverse incentives and barriers for researchers working in contexts of minimal scientific investment.

The session was structured around three learning outcomes:

- that participants would understand how nonprofit publishing models can broaden participation and support fairer research assessment;
- that they would learn the legal and rights-related principles that support community-driven approaches to publishing;
- and that they could explain how Diamond OA can reduce barriers, expand inclusion, and strengthen research communities across different regions.

Registration reach

The geographic distribution of registrations speaks directly to the cross-regional design of the series. Europe accounted for just under half of the audience, reflecting the project's institutional base and existing communication channels. Africa and Latin America together accounted for forty-two per cent of registrations. The *Other* category, composed largely of registrations from North America and Asia, indicates a level of global interest in the topic that the subsequent webinars and ambassador outreach can build on.

Region	Registrations	Share
Europe	119	46.7%
Africa	67	26.3%
Latin America	40	15.7%
Other	29	11.4%
Total	255	100%

Table 2. Regional breakdown of registrations for the first webinar (n = 255).

The professional composition of the audience is equally informative. Research support professionals, librarians, publishing and editorial staff, and those in administration and management, made up the clear majority of registrations (73%), underscoring the theme’s relevance to those directly responsible for running and supporting journals. Researchers and academics, including PhD candidates, formed a substantial further share (24%), with the small remainder drawn from policy, funder and civil-society roles (3%). Taken together, this mix suggests the event reached precisely the intermediaries and active participants in the scholarly communication ecosystem the task aims to engage, rather than a narrower advocacy audience.

Professional role	Registrations	Share
Research support professional	187	73.3%
Researcher	60	23.5%
Other	8	3.1%
Total	255	100%

Table 3. Distribution of webinar registrants by professional role (n = 255)

Second Webinar

The second event in the Discussion Series, *From Preprints to Publication: How Community-Driven Models Are Reshaping Scholarly Communication*, was held on 11 June 2026 as a ninety-minute online session. Building on the first webinar, which set out the rationale for Diamond Open Access, this event turned to the question of how community-governed publishing takes shape in practice.

Theme, speakers, and outputs

The webinar explored the emerging Publish-Review-Curate (PRC) model as a community-governed pathway for scholarly publishing, and its potential to operate within Diamond Open Access and nonprofit principles. It considered the model both as an infrastructure and as a process, engaging with key Open Science concepts such as preprints, open peer review, and curation. Through perspectives from the three regions represented in ALMASI, the session invited participants to reflect on how community-driven approaches to publishing are taking shape across different contexts.

The session opened with Zehra Taşkın (Hacettepe University, Institute of Informatics; TSV), who set the scene with an overview of the Diamond Open Access landscape across Africa, Europe, and Latin America, drawing on the findings of the ALMASI scoping report to frame the discussion that follows.

D5.5 Report on engagement of researchers 1

Femi Qudus Arogundade brought an African perspective through COPPHA PublishNow, reflecting on how community-driven publishing connects to Diamond OA and nonprofit principles.

Patricia Pedri contributed a Latin American perspective grounded in her expertise on open peer review and Open Science.

Thomas Guillemaud shared a European perspective through Peer Community In and the Peer Community Journal, presenting community-governed publishing as both infrastructure and process.

Similarly to the first webinar, there were specific learning objectives that we aimed to achieve:

- that participants would be able to describe the role of preprints in contemporary scholarly communication, and explain how they enable early dissemination and open engagement with research outputs;
- that they would be able to analyse how open peer review reshapes scholarly evaluation, and assess its contribution to transparency, quality, and researcher agency;
- that they would be able to understand post-review curation and journal publication as community-governed activities, and discuss how they support sustainable, nonprofit pathways for scholarly publishing;
- and that they would be able to evaluate how these practices come together in emerging models such as Publish-Review-Curate, and compare how community-driven approaches are taking shape across the European, African, and Latin American contexts represented in ALMASI.

As the webinar fell at the very close of the reporting period, the discussion it generated will be documented in the final engagement report (D5.10). The registration profile of the event, however, can already be reported here. A total of 414 people registered for the webinar. These final figures offer a strong and reliable picture of the webinar's reach and of the communities the ALMASI engagement work is mobilising. Two dimensions of the registrant profile are summarised below: geographic region and professional role.

The regional distribution confirmed that the webinar reached the three target regions of ALMASI in broadly balanced proportions, with Europe and Latin America each accounting for just over a third of registrations and a substantial African contingent, underlining the programme's tri-regional reach.

Region	Registrations	Share
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Europe	146	35.3%
Latin America	143	34.5%
Africa	75	18.1%
Other	50	12.1%
Total	414	100%

Table 4. Regional breakdown of registrations for the first webinar (n = 414).

Finally, the professional profile of registrants shows research support professionals (librarians, research managers and publishing professionals) as the largest group, followed by researchers, with the remainder drawn from students, policy, funding and civil-society backgrounds. This mix reflects the webinar's positioning at the intersection of research practice and the infrastructure that supports scholar-led publishing.

Professional role	Registrations	Share
Research support professional	201	48.6%
Researcher	162	39.1%
Other	51	12.3%
Total	414	100%

Table 5. Distribution of webinar registrants by professional role (n = 414)

ALMASI Ambassador Programme

Application reach

The open call for the ALMASI Ambassador Programme lasted approximately two months, from 17 November 2025 to 15 January 2026, with 155 applications received. Of these, 114 applicants confirmed their continued interest in response to the follow-up confirmation email and formed the initial cohort, all of whom were invited to indicate their availability for the launch sessions in March 2026.. The figures reported in this section refer to the full applicant pool, as this is the measure that best captures the reach of the call and the level of interest it generated across the scholarly communication community.

The geographic distribution of applications reflects both the opportunities and the limitations of the dissemination strategy pursued during the open call. Africa accounted for almost three-quarters of applications, a response pattern attributable to the early circulation of the call through the African Scholarly Communication mailing list. The "Other" category, comprising applicants from outside the project's core geography, principally Asia and North America, constitutes the second-largest group and reflects wider international interest in Diamond OA. Latin America and Europe each produced smaller cohorts.

Figure 1. Regional distribution of applications to the ALMASI Ambassador Programme (n = 155).

The professional composition of the applicant pool confirms that the call reached precisely the intermediary communities the programme was designed to engage. Researchers and academics, together with library and information services staff, account for 58% (combined) of the applications, providing a strong foundation for the programme's dual focus on the researcher-ambassador role and on editor and information-professional engagement. Administration and management staff, typically in senior positions within universities, libraries, or journals, make up a further seventeen per cent, and publishing and editorial staff contribute another 14%. Smaller but strategically relevant cohorts came from open science and open access professionals, communications and outreach staff, and technical and IT roles. Taken together, the mix suggests a cohort well positioned to carry ALMASI messages into the editorial, research, and support communities that sustain nonprofit and Diamond Open Access publishing.

Figure 2. Professional role breakdown of applications to the ALMASI Ambassador Programme, based on a categorisation of self-reported position titles (n = 155).

These figures describe the reach of the call rather than the cohort's trajectory, which will be assessed in the final engagement report at M36. What they already demonstrate is that the programme succeeded in attracting a geographically diverse and professionally varied pool of candidates.

Launch sessions and active cohort

Following the confirmation email process⁷, 114 ambassadors confirmed their continued interest in proceeding with the programme and entered the launch phase. The launch took place across seven online sessions held in March 2026, designed to accommodate different time zones and language preferences across the ambassador cohort. Sessions were configured to deliver a consistent orientation to the programme while allowing smaller groups to engage more directly with us. The figures that follow describe the effective reach of this launch and, together with the application figures above, trace the trajectory from expression of interest through to active participation in the programme.

Figure 3. Trajectory from application to active participation in the Ambassador Programme.

Of the 114 confirmed ambassadors, 90 indicated when they were available and were invited to a specific launch session accordingly. 61 attended the session to which they were invited. A further 24 ambassadors confirmed their interest but did not engage with any of the launch sessions, and 29 were invited but did not attend on the day⁸. The overall attendance rate

⁷ An email was sent to the applicants asking them to confirm their continued interest in this activity. This was the first filtering step to understand who of the applicants genuinely wanted to invest time in the ambassadorial programme.

⁸ One clarification is important here: ambassadors who have not yet participated in all planned activities will still be considered for future communications. As ambassadors are aware, full acknowledgement as an ambassador, and association with the project, requires completing at least some of the activities planned for this cohort. We have therefore chosen a more flexible, less rigid approach to defining who counts as an ambassador, in the hope that this will encourage participation over the longer term.

among invited ambassadors was 67.8%, a strong level of engagement for a volunteer online cohort of this scale. The session-level breakdown is presented below.

Session	Invited	Present	Absent	Attendance rate
Session 1	39	26	13	66.7%
Session 2	24	17	7	70.8%
Session 3	10	8	2	80.0%
Session 4	8	7	1	87.5%
Session 6	2	1	1	50.0%
Session 7	3	1	2	33.3%
Session 8	4	1	3	25.0%
Total	90	61	29	67.8%

Table 6. Breakdown of launch session attendance. Session numbering reflects the sequence in which sessions were delivered; Session 5 had no registrations and does not appear in the table.

The working cohort at the end of the launch phase therefore stands at 61 active ambassadors⁹. While this represents a substantial reduction from the 155 applications originally received, it is well above the cohort size of twenty to thirty that the team held as a working assumption during the design phase, and provides a distributed capacity across all regions that is sufficient to support the local events, mentoring, and translation activities planned for the delivery phase of the programme.

A comparison of the regional distribution of applications and active ambassadors shows how conversion varied across regions. Africa retained the largest share of the cohort in both absolute and proportional terms, while Europe and Latin America each increased their share slightly between application and active participation. The "Other" group, applicants outside the project's core geography, mainly in Asia, had the lowest conversion rate, consistent with the programme's intended regional focus.

⁹ The "active" term is used for those who steadily follow the activities as and when they are created.

Figure 4. Regional distribution of applications compared with active ambassadors who participated in at least one launch session. Values above the bars show absolute counts.

Taken together, the launch phase confirms that the programme was able to translate the strong initial interest into a working cohort with representation in each of the three core ALMASI regions, and that the rates of conversion from application to active participation were in fact higher in Europe and Latin America than in Africa, counterbalancing to some extent the regional imbalance observed at the application stage.

Key concepts across the launch sessions

The launch sessions followed a consistent structure across regions, built around a shared set of concepts that framed the Ambassador Programme for the incoming community. The following themes recurred throughout.

Situating the programme within ALMASI

Each session opened by placing the programme within the wider ALMASI project and its four objectives. Particular care was taken to present Diamond Open Access as more than a fee-free business model, introducing it instead as a model that encompasses quality, open science practices, and community ownership of editorial processes and content. This framing grounded the ambassador role in the conceptual backbone of the project rather than in publishing logistics alone.

Reciprocal exchange across three regions

A recurring theme was that the programme is not a one-directional effort to persuade researchers to adopt Diamond Open Access, but a genuinely reciprocal exchange in which Africa, Europe, and Latin America learn from one another. The sessions gave deliberate weight to South-to-South and South-to-North knowledge flows, acknowledging that attitudes in many parts of the Global South are already favourable to Diamond Open Access and that established landscapes, such as those in Latin America, offer practices from which the rest of the project can learn.

The ambassador role as a multiplier

The role itself was framed as a network of peers and a multiplier mechanism rather than a broadcasting channel. Ambassadors were invited to share project outputs through the channels they already use, to support local events, to contribute to co-authoring and mentoring, and to translate key materials into the languages of their communities, with the relationship understood as mutual: the project provides materials, opportunities, and support, while ambassadors contribute their knowledge, networks, and local insight.

Foundational principles and the Code of Conduct

The sessions introduced the principles that underpin the programme and its Code of Conduct. These rest on equity, community governance, and the treatment of knowledge as a public good, alongside a non-negotiable commitment to non-commercial, community-driven publishing and to inclusivity across regions, languages, and cultures. Since the launch phase, all ambassadors have been provided with the Code of Conduct and are expected to confirm receipt and acknowledge having read it.

Practical boundaries of the role

Practical boundaries were set out clearly. These included the separation of the ambassador role from any personal or commercial activity, the independence of the programme from journal indexing decisions, the expectation that ambassadors represent the project only within the scope agreed with the coordination team, and the responsible use of the shared mailing list. Transparency in the use of artificial intelligence emerged as a further shared principle, reflecting a commitment to declaring when and how such tools are used rather than prohibiting them.

A convergence space shaped by ambassadors

Each session closed with a structured discussion that allowed ambassadors to raise the topics and skills they wished to explore, to identify their primary audiences, and to share what they felt others should understand about open access publishing in their own contexts. These discussions reinforced the intended character of the programme as a convergence space where communities meet and help shape its direction together.

5. Added Value perspectives

This section synthesises the added value of Diamond OA and nonprofit scholarly publishing as articulated during the first event of the ALMASI Discussion Series, held in December 2025¹⁰. The talking points presented below are extracted and classified in alignment with

¹⁰ Readers can access the discussion via the recording in [Youtube](#), or via the [Slides in Zenodo](#).

Deliverable D5.2¹¹ – ALMASI Talking points for Diamond OA. Three researchers spoke from African, European, and Latin American vantage points: Dr Philip Mwachaka, drawing on his experience editing the East African Journal of Neurological Sciences; Ginevra Peruginelli, framing the model as a question of rights, commons, and the public mission of universities; and Dr Luciana Balboa, placing Diamond OA within a Latin American tradition of community-driven publishing and research assessment reform.

Their contributions have been grouped thematically below. Section 5.1 addresses the added values that Diamond OA and nonprofit journals offer to researchers. Section 5.2 addresses how publishers and advocates can communicate these values and the actions needed to sustain them. Each subsection closes with a summary that ALMASI ambassadors and editors can adapt for use in their own contexts.

5.1 Researchers

Theme A: Access without financial barriers

Diamond OA removes the two barriers that weigh most heavily on researchers in resource-limited settings: the publication fee and the reading fee.

Talking point

Diamond OA is extremely important to researchers, especially those from resource-limited areas. People can read your articles for free, and as an author, you can publish freely without article processing fees.

Most commercial publishers charge high article processing fees and restrict access behind paywalls. Either way, researchers in low and middle-income countries are excluded.

Relying on international commercial publishers, with prohibitively expensive subscriptions and APCs, makes the national research system vulnerable.

Theme B: Rights retention and author control

Diamond OA keeps rights with authors rather than transferring them to a commercial publisher, preserving researchers' control over how their work circulates and is reused.

Talking point

Authors retain the rights and control of their articles or manuscripts.

¹¹ Davidson, A., Proudman, V., Lujano, I., Kuchma, I., Murray, S., Mora-Campos, A., Becerril-García, A., Estrada-Medina, M., Debano, I., & Bassinet, A. (2025). ALMASI Talking points for Diamond OA (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17943492>.

Talking point

Researchers must be aware of what they sign, and retain their rights wherever possible. But they cannot confront commercial publishers alone, so they need institutional backing.

Most research is publicly funded and done in public institutions. When we publish, handing copyright to commercial publishers turns public knowledge into private property, systematically and silently.

Theme C: Equity and participation in global science

By removing both cost and access barriers, Diamond OA broadens participation in scholarly communication, with particular benefits for early-career researchers and researchers in the Global South.

Talking point

Diamond OA expands participation in global science. All of us can publish our research without barriers, which improves visibility and supports equity and scientific justice.

Diamond OA is a pathway for research equity, visibility and scientific sovereignty in Africa and the Global South.

It empowers early career researchers, who suffer significantly because most funders support established researchers rather than those at the start of their careers.

Diamond OA enables early career researchers to publish freely and, by doing so, enhances the visibility of African science globally.

Diamond OA strengthens regional research ecosystems. Once open access is in place, researchers are encouraged to publish without fear of fees.

Theme D: Alignment with the public mission of research

Publishing in Diamond OA aligns researchers' practice with the public and ethical foundations of scholarship: publicly funded knowledge remains in the public domain, consistent with the human right to science.

Talking point

International human rights instruments recognise a right to science. Everyone should be able to participate in scientific progress and benefit from its results.

What society pays to produce, it must then pay again to access. Diamond OA is a correction to this.

When scholars and institutions keep ownership and rights, governance remains collective and aligned with the public mission of research. When ownership is transferred, governance follows commercial interest and shifts toward market logic.

Talking point

In Latin America, science is predominantly funded by the state. In that sense, science is not viewed as a commodity, but as a public good.

Diamond OA restores both the legal and the scholarly commons.

5.2 Publishers and Advocacy

The following thematic clusters bring together talking points on how publishers and advocates can communicate the added value of Diamond OA and the actions needed to sustain it. They are intended as a shared resource for the ALMASI ambassador network and for editors advocating for Diamond OA in their own institutions and regions.

Theme A: Define Diamond OA through governance and ownership, not fees alone

A journal that charges no author fee is not automatically Diamond. The defining question is who owns the journal, who governs it, and in whose interest it operates.

Talking point

Ownership is not just a legal formality. It defines the accountability, the trust, and the sustainability of scholarly communication.

Journals must clearly articulate their mission, aims, and scope on their websites. Governance has to be scholar-driven. Editorial boards should be appointed through transparent and accountable procedures. Journals are not assets; they are communities.

When scholars and institutions keep ownership and rights, governance remains collective and aligned with the public mission of research.

Theme B: Advocate for research assessment reform

The added value of Diamond OA remains partially blocked as long as researchers are rewarded for publishing in commercially indexed journals. Advocacy for Diamond OA and advocacy for research assessment reform are inseparable.

Talking point

Metrics work against Diamond OA, because they push researchers toward journals whose prestige comes from commercial indexes, while Diamond OA journals, being community-run and nonprofit, face an unfair contest for visibility and impact in the same commercial arena.

Talking point
The foremost priority is to connect the tradition of science as a common good with our evaluation practices. This shift extends beyond adjusting indicators. It requires a transformation of the values underlying the evaluation system.
It is crucial to prioritise concepts such as social impact, local relevance, and democratic access to knowledge as key axes for an evaluation model that resonates with regional needs.
The strengths and tradition of regional publishing are not yet fully acknowledged in our research evaluation systems.
Join CoARA, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. It is a global initiative that allows communities to contribute collectively to transforming the scientific evaluation ecosystem.

Theme C: Pursue rights retention and legal protection at the institutional and national level

Institutional and national policy are the leverage points that make rights retention effective in practice.

Talking point
Universities have a legal and ethical duty to protect researchers' rights through open licensing policies, contract review, and investment in public infrastructure.
Researchers need institutional backing to retain their rights because they cannot confront commercial publishers alone.
Governments must play a central role by legislating to ensure that publicly funded knowledge cannot be appropriated by private actors.
When communities, universities, or national consortia act collectively, they can rebalance negotiating power, challenge commercial dominance, and build more equitable community publishing models.

Theme D: Invest in shared infrastructure, training, and quality

The case for Diamond OA becomes concrete when publishers and advocates can point to specific support for infrastructure, training, and quality assurance. These are the areas where community journals need coordinated backing most.

Talking point
Diamond OA can be strengthened in resource-limited areas through regional collaboration and shared infrastructure. Common platforms such as OJS (Open Journal Systems), together with institutional and government support, allow journals to share the burden of hosting and technical work.

Talking point

Training for editors, reviewers, and authors on manuscript writing and review improves the quality of articles published in open access venues. Improving metadata and indexing strategies increases visibility.

Limited indexing of emerging journals, together with technical infrastructure limitations such as metadata handling and IT access, are persistent challenges for Diamond OA journals.

Obtaining a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) has long been a challenge across Latin America, not only in Argentina.

Theme E: Communicate sustainability honestly and secure coordinated funding

Volunteer labour and goodwill are real strengths of Diamond OA, but they cannot substitute for a funding model. Naming the actual cost of running community journals makes coordinated investment possible.

Talking point

Most Diamond OA journals depend on volunteers. Attracting editors and reviewers can be difficult when they expect to be paid.

Every peso invested in research through the Diamond route returns knowledge that is immediately and freely available to society, maximising the social return on investment and fostering innovation.

Making access to foreign subscriptions and APCs (Article Processing Charges) prohibitively expensive makes the national research system vulnerable.

In Latin America, science is predominantly funded by the state. Science is not viewed as a commodity, but as a public good.

6. Plan and next steps

This final section looks ahead to the work that remains. Having set out the rationale and design of the two T5.3 workstreams, it now turns to where each is headed over the remainder of the project. The Ambassador Programme and the Discussion Series have each been carefully designed, with clear plans to guide activity in the months ahead. What follows outlines the immediate priorities and milestones for each, before considering how both might intersect with the learning pathways under development in WP3 and the wider training material the project is producing.

Ambassadors Programme

The Ambassador Programme was designed with a portfolio of activities for ambassadors to engage with based on their interests, expertise, and available time. These activities are intended to unfold progressively over the programme period (2026 to 2027), beginning with orientation and community building and moving toward substantive collaborative outputs.

Local and regional events. Ambassadors will be invited to propose and co-organise events that promote Diamond OA in their local or regional contexts. A structured event proposal form was developed to allow ambassadors to submit proposals that include the event title, venue, date, format, target audience, rationale, and the type of support requested from the ALMASI project (which may include Zoom infrastructure, co-hosting, or speakers). An accompanying organising checklist, adapted from the ALMASI forums guide, provides practical guidance on session planning and delivery. We emphasised that ALMASI support for events would be provided selectively, given that the programme cannot scale co-hosting to all 100+ ambassadors, and that the primary goal is to empower ambassadors to lead events independently with project resources and branding support.

Mentoring sessions. A programme of closed mentoring sessions, distinct from the public Discussion Series, is planned to build ambassador capacity on specific topics. The first mentoring session concept we developed is “How to Talk About Diamond OA,” which will include a practical component led by the DOAJ. Subsequent sessions will be shaped by the interests and needs expressed by ambassadors during and after the launch sessions.

Translation and co-authorship. Ambassadors with relevant language skills will be invited to contribute to the translation of ALMASI project outputs or to co-author blog posts and short articles for the ALMASI website, potentially beyond the official languages of ALMASI (English, French, Spanish, Portuguese). We will provide thematic guidance, linking contributions to specific outputs such as training materials, scoping reports, and landscape analyses from other work packages. All content for the ALMASI website is subject to our editorial review. These contributions are voluntary and intended for ambassadors with genuine expertise and interest, rather than as a general obligation.

Glossary work. The ALMASI project glossary, available in four languages, will be shared with ambassadors as a reference resource, with the possibility of collaborative glossary development sessions. These activities position ambassadors not only as advocates but as active contributors to the project’s educational outputs.

Advocacy and peer communication. Underpinning all of the above is the ambassadors’ core function as peer communicators. Through their existing institutional networks, scholarly associations, social media presence, and professional relationships, ambassadors amplify the visibility of Diamond OA and the ALMASI project. The programme provides them with resources, talking points, and a supportive community to draw on. Still, the model's power

lies in the fact that the message reaches researchers through trusted, familiar voices rather than through centralised project communications.

Discussion Series

The Discussion Series on Scholar-led Publishing will continue to develop as a space where ALMASI engages researcher communities in dialogue, identifying themes of shared interest and building partnerships around them. Following the first webinar in December 2025 on reclaiming knowledge and ownership, inspired by OA Week, the second event in June 2026 will turn to the Publish-Review-Curate model, reflecting on its adoption within researcher communities and its close alignment with Diamond OA scholarly infrastructure.

For subsequent webinars, we will draw on scholarly publishing literature on researcher engagement with Diamond OA and research practice including the development of peer review models and review platforms, as well as the emerging role of artificial intelligence in scholarly communication. These signals will be complemented by ideas from the ALMASI partners, discussions at key conferences around Diamond OA (e.g.. Global Summit on Diamond OA¹²), and proposals from the ALMASI International Advisory Board, ensuring that the series remains responsive to the questions circulating in the wider research community.

Collaboration with WP3 and Training Material

In collaboration with Task 3.1 (Curriculum Development), ambassadors will be invited to participate in sprints to develop and review training materials for Diamond OA publishing. Co-creation is key to ensure the quality of outputs. The sprints are designed to be mutually reinforcing, with ambassadors contributing to the curriculum while strengthening their own engagement with the project. The operational framework for ambassadors' engagement within the broader ALMASI capacity-building ecosystem includes a structured alignment between Tasks 3.1, 3.3, and 3.4. Below we list some key perspectives and contributions from Ambassadors and other stakeholders of the project:

- **Regional perspectives:** ambassadors bring context and language sensitivity from their communities, helping ensure that training materials speak meaningfully to audiences across the ALMASI regions.
- **Testing and refinement:** materials are reviewed against the realities of editors, researchers, and research support professionals in different settings, improving their relevance and usability.
- **Co-creation of content:** stakeholders actively contribute to developing learning resources rather than receiving them as finished products.

¹² See here the website of the Global Summit on Diamond OA: <https://www.diamondoasummit.org/>

- **Capacity building:** participation in the sprints deepens ambassadors' own knowledge of Diamond OA publishing and strengthens their role as multipliers.
- **Extended ambassador role:** the collaboration positions ambassadors as active contributors to the curriculum underpinning ALMASI's longer-term work, beyond outreach and dissemination. Ambassadors are envisioned not only as dissemination actors, but as contributors to community mapping exercises, regional needs identification, and the adaptation of training pathways before pilot implementation.

The collaboration between Task 5.3 and WP3 goes beyond the Curriculum Development (T3.1), as Task 3.4, responsible for National Capacity Centers (NCCs) and Communities of Practices (CoP) coordination and capacity building delivery, has a direct connection with the Ambassadors Programme. The two task teams are coordinated to identify opportunities for ambassadors to act as a contact point or, maybe, co-organisers for training activities delivered through the NCC and the CoP networks. This link will be set up before the first training pilot planned for Milestone 5 (October 2026)

The collaboration of ambassadors with WP3 will be defined later on given that the process of aligning the material selection and delivery (Task 3.3) and the final coordination of the communities (Task 3.4) is still ongoing.

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Annex

1. Information Pack for ALMASI Ambassadors Programme

Welcome to the ALMASI Ambassadors Programme.

This Information pack brings together everything you need from the launch session: **the recording, the slides, a summary of the discussion in the four project languages**, and the **Code of Conduct** with the two actions every ambassador is asked to complete.

1. Launch session recording

- The full recording of the launch webinar, covering the project overview, the Ambassadors Programme, the Code of Conduct, and the ambassador discussion.
- Watch the recording: [link]¹³

2. Launch session slides

- The slides used during the session, available for your reference.
- Open the slides: [link]

3. Launch session summary (EN, FR, PT, ES)

- A written summary of the launch session, available in the four project languages.
 - English: [link]
 - Français : [link]
 - Português: [link]
 - Español: [link]

4. A summary of what we expect from Ambassadors:

- Share ALMASI outputs and updates through your channels, including webinars, training, and new publications.
- Engage occasionally, not daily: two ambassador meetings per year, plus optional General Assemblies and mentoring sessions.
- Propose and co-host local events with the coordination team, in your institutional, national, or regional context.
- Contribute when you can: short blog posts, translations into local languages, reviews of deliverables, or piloting of training materials.
- Coordinate before representing ALMASI publicly, so you receive branded slides and aligned messaging.
- Follow the Code of Conduct in all programme-related communication and activities.

5. Code of Conduct and required actions

- The Code of Conduct sets out the standards of behaviour for the 2026–2027 programme period.
- Two actions are required of every ambassador:

¹³ Links have been disabled because these are internal files and not for public use.

- Declare any conflict of interest.
- Acknowledge that you have read and agreed to the Code of Conduct.
- Read the Code of Conduct: [link]
- Complete both actions in one short form: [link]

Questions? Contact the coordination team at fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org or virginia.pablo@fecyt.es

2. ALMASI Ambassadors Programme (2026–2027): Code of Conduct

Introduction / Purpose

The ALMASI (Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally) Ambassadors Programme brings together researchers, librarians, and community leaders from across Africa, Europe, and Latin America to promote Diamond Open Access (OA) and the outputs of the ALMASI project in an inclusive and professional way.

This Code of Conduct defines and explains the standards of behaviour for all ALMASI Ambassadors to create a safe, respectful, and inclusive environment.

Scope

This Code of Conduct applies to ALMASI ambassadors when they are participating in, contributing to, or representing the ALMASI Ambassadors Programme or the ALMASI project.

This applies to participation in:

- Ambassador meetings and assemblies (in-person or online).
- Local events organised by ambassadors under this programme.
- Online engagement in the role of ambassador (e. g., social media, messaging platforms, mailing lists).
- Public settings where ambassadors represent ALMASI.

Core Values /Principles

Ambassadors are expected to uphold the following core values:

- Integrity, respect and professionalism
- Inclusion and equity in participation
- Responsible communication
- Respect privacy and confidentiality
- Positive, constructive and collaborative engagement

Behavioural Standards

Ambassadors are expected to represent the ALMASI project in a professional, ethical, and respectful manner in all contexts, whether at events, in publications, on online platforms, or in interactions with stakeholders. All interactions should be guided by principles of equity, inclusiveness, and mutual respect, recognising the diversity of individuals, disciplines, and cultural contexts involved in the programme.

Ambassadors should promote the programme and the ALMASI project accurately, honestly, and responsibly, and are expected to foster positive dialogue, knowledge exchange, and cooperation within the ambassador network and the broader scholarly community.

Ambassadors should follow applicable laws, institutional policies, and professional standards, and act with sensitivity to cultural norms in the regions where they operate. Confidential information and personal data obtained through the programme must be handled responsibly and in line with data protection principles.

The following conduct is not acceptable and may lead to removal from the programme:

- Discrimination based on gender, gender identity or expression, sexual orientation, ethnicity, nationality, language, religion, disability, age, academic status, or any other personal characteristic.
- Bullying, intimidation, coercion, harassment (including sexual harassment), or any behaviour that creates a hostile or unsafe environment for others.
- Incitement to hatred or violence against individuals or groups, whether directly or indirectly, including through social media or events linked to ALMASI activities.
- Hate speech in any form, spoken, written, or online.
- Misrepresentation or distortion of the aims, values, activities, or outcomes of the ALMASI project.
- Misuse of personal data or confidential information obtained through the programme.
- Plagiarism, improper attribution, or unauthorised use of others' work, ideas, or materials.

Programme Scope and Responsibilities

The following provisions clarify the boundaries of the ambassador role and the appropriate use of the ALMASI name and resources.

Conflict of Interest

The ALMASI name, branding, and affiliation must not be associated with any business, commercial, or professional activities of individual ambassadors. This includes, but is not limited to, commercial OJS installations, paid technical services, or consulting activities. Ambassadors must ensure a clear separation between their role in the programme and any personal or professional interests that could create a real or perceived conflict of interest.

Indexing Services Disclaimer

Ambassadors have no relationship to journal indexing services by virtue of their participation in the programme. Involvement in ALMASI activities does not influence, facilitate, or imply any connection to decisions regarding the indexing of journals in any service. Ambassadors must not represent or imply otherwise.

Scope of Representation

The ALMASI Ambassadors Programme is specifically focused on engaging and communicating on Diamond OA publishing. Ambassadors are not expected or authorised to represent the ALMASI project independently beyond the activities coordinated through the programme. When participating in events or communications linked to ALMASI, ambassadors will act within the scope agreed with the programme coordination team.

Use of the Ambassador Mailing List

The ambassador mailing list is provided for programme-related communication only. It must not be used for personal promotion, commercial purposes, unsolicited content, or any communication unrelated to the objectives of the programme.

Reporting and Compliance

If an ambassador experiences or observes behaviour that goes against this Code of Conduct, they should report it to the designated ALMASI contacts:

- Fotis Mystakopoulos (fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org)
- Virginia de Pablo Llorente (virginia.pablo@fecyt.es)

All ambassadors are expected to cooperate in such reviews to maintain a safe and respectful community.

Acknowledgement

By joining the ALMASI Ambassadors Programme, all participants agree to follow this Code of Conduct during the 2026–2027 programme period.

Action: Declare Conflict of Interest, and Acknowledge reading the CoC here.